

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN GRP

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Abstract

The effect of damage on the flexural strength of small plates was measured. The types of damage included impact and holes; the matrix material and fibre configuration was varied. Overall changes were analysed to show the effect of matrix ductility and to obtain simple normalisations for plate geometry, fibre content and severity of damage. A low cost method for materials selection is demonstrated and a simple design method to allow for damage in structures is proposed.

Introduction and Summary of Preliminary Results

It is a commonly held view that the damage resistance and impact properties of a composite may be improved by increasing the toughness of the matrix. The verification of such opinions would require the provision of a large quantity of experimental data on a range of material systems tested under equivalent conditions. Such data are hard to come by. If a common standard has been used it is often an Izod or Charpy flexed beam test. These may not adequately reflect the behaviour of plate-like structures subjected to biaxial loading which is the more usual service impact condition. Comparisons between systems made using differing test methods are erroneous and misleading. A recent study into the effect of material variables on the impact properties of a wide range of glass reinforced plastic composites (GRP) has provided some surprising results (1). Instead of testing a statistically meaningful set of specimens for each GRP system, a single specimen was used and all specimens were evaluated as though they belonged to a single data set. A total of eighteen specimens were produced with combinations of three reinforcement configurations and seven resin systems. The fibres were arranged as woven roving, chopped strand mat and a combination of the two, and the resin systems ranged from a cold cure epoxy, through an isophthalic polyester to a urethane-acrylate. All specimens possessed different thicknesses and volume fractions of glass varied considerably according to the nature of the reinforcement. Despite all of these variations, the results of falling weight impact tests when normalised to allow for the thickness and volume fraction variations, behaved as a single data set with a coefficient of variation (9.9%) similar to that exhibited by a set of specimens taken from a single sheet of one system (9.8%), see figure 1. These results prompted further studies which sought to investigate the concept of damage in GRP in more depth as well as the practical differences between material combinations.

Figure 2 shows the results obtained from slowly deforming a 60mm x 60mm plate in two ways. One deformation mode involved centrally loading the plate which was supported on a steel ring 40 mm in diameter. This was made exactly equivalent to the falling weight impact test albeit at a slower rate of test. The force-time curves are similar to those produced during impact in almost every detail with the exception that the magnitude of the forces in impact are almost double those generated during slow testing (as indeed would be expected from a simplistic comparison of dynamic and static loading). Figure 2 shows little difference between a brittle matrix system and a ductile matrix system. The second deformation mode, which has been subsequently adopted during this work is in effect a three-point bend test performed on a plate using a span of 40mm. Under this testing regime there does appear to be a significant difference related to the matrix. However the most important outcome of the initial results was probably a decision to look actively for commonality between GRP systems rather than to identify differences in detail. This approach recognises that while there may well be absolute differences in the mean behaviour of particular GRP types, these differences may not be particularly significant in the context of the variability. There are batch to batch variations and conservative safety factors in design are used. Furthermore, manufacturing considerations may introduce more significant variations in properties than those resulting from material changes. This is illustrated for the case of injection moulded SMC as

shown in figure 3. A box type of specimen has been moulded in a cavity which had a flow obstructor offset from the injection gate. The X-radiograph illustrates the flow induced fibre orientation within the component. The box was subjected to a total of seven identical very low energy impacts at different positions. The consequence is a series of cracks of magnitude which is a function of position : the cracks map the flow induced local orientation that has geometric constraints imposed by the shape of the component. The variation in crack length is very pronounced.

When various GRP systems with a range of ductile and brittle matrices are subjected to impact, the fine detail of the damage created differs from material to material : in short term tests the effects of this damage appear to be similar. A system for quantifying the magnitude of damage was introduced which recognised this fact and measured the severity of damage solely on the basis of the extent of the visibly damaged area and not on the nature of this damage. On a test specimen the width across the area of damage was measured and subtracted from the specimen width; this undamaged width was used as an indicator of the residual integrity under short term testing. In order to explore the general validity of this parameter, damage was introduced into specimens by deforming them slowly in a tension-compression frame and by removing material by drilling a hole, as well as by varying impact energy. The results of this exercise, figure 4, revealed that the remaining strengths of laminates tested by the three-point bend test were linearly dependant on the extent of damage irrespective of the method of its introduction. Furthermore, although there were subtle differences in the residual strengths of specimens subjected to impact slow indentation and drilling, the drilled hole provided a good slightly conservative indication of the effects of all damage states and therefore could act as a reference damage state. The effect of damaging a piece of GRP is equivalent to removing that piece of damaged material. No stress concentrating effect associated with damage has been observed. The additional results presented here seek to demonstrate the general applicability of this approach. It would be advantageous if the residual properties of damaged GRP could be predicted without detailed knowledge of the cause of the damage. Preferably this would be based merely on the area of damage together with the known effect of removing material with a comparable area and be measured by a simple test.

Materials and Test Methods

The materials used in this part of the study consisted of two GRP types, both comprising a random chopped strand mat reinforcement. One (GRP7) had a general purpose isophthalic polyester resin matrix which in this context may be considered to be relatively brittle, and the other (GRP8) a urethane-acrylate resin which is comparatively tough. The thicknesses and volume fractions of the specimens varied somewhat but were in the region of 4mm and 20%. The test methods fell into two categories, those used to induce damage and those used to assess damage. Damage was induced both by a falling weight impact test where a 20 mm diameter striker impacted a 60mm x 60mm specimen supported on a 40 mm steel ring and by slow indentation. For that the impact test rig was mounted on a tension-compression frame and tests performed at much slower rates. Additional methods of inducing damage were to machine into the specimen holes which took the form of either a single hole in the centre of the plate or multiple holes along a line bisecting the plate. A final method involved hammering a coarse nail through the plate which induced both a hole and an associated area of damage. In all cases the severity of the damage was assessed solely by measuring the width of undamaged material (in the case of the nail this included an allowance for the damage zone around the hole itself). The method of assessing damage was confined to bend tests on damaged plates, but the dimensions of the specimens and the bending span have been systematically varied. The majority of tests were performed using a standard test geometry of a 60 mm wide test plate on a 40mm span. Additional tests were performed using a 15mm span; the specimen sizes were the usual 60mm x 60mm, plus a narrow version 10mm wide and a small bar 25mm long and 10mm wide.

Results

The effect of introducing a hole of a given diameter was found to be equivalent to introducing a series of holes of a similar total diameter. This is shown in figure 5 where the remaining strength of plates versus the undamaged width is plotted. The results from plates tested after puncturing by a nail are also shown on that figure. There is a linear relationship between undamaged width and strength regardless of the type or arrangement of damage. The value of the holes as a comparative method for both discriminating between materials and predicting the effects of damage may be observed from figure 6. Here in figure 6a, the effect of single holes on the residual strength of the brittle GRP 7 and the ductile GRP 8 is found to be similar. Strength reductions occur that are linearly dependant on undamaged area and extrapolate back to the origin. The materials are shown to be different in terms of the actual strength at any particular damage state but this is primarily a consequence of the higher undamaged strength of the GRP7. Figure 6b

contains the same data with the addition of results from a variety of damage sources; the trends are maintained although the scatter is slightly worse.

The final set of data concerns bend tests where the geometry was varied. Figure 7 shows the results from GRP7. The specimens were undamaged, a central hole was regarded as a method of varying the width of the plate. The results from the bend tests are plotted as strength (maximum force) versus a geometric normalisation parameter - thickness x width / span. These results all fall on a single line passing through the origin.

Discussion

The remarkable observation from this work is that, in bending, residual strength of GRP whilst being dependent on the area of damage, is grossly insensitive to the specific nature of an event that introduces the damage. The implication is that holes and other forms of damage do not act as stress concentrators as is common in other materials but simply act to cause a net reduction in the available material support. This observation coupled with the simple effect of geometric variables on the bend strength of laminates, suggests that very elementary approaches to the design of GRP structures may be fruitful; if the effect of a series of holes of a given size is known, then the effects of any in-service damage process such as impact may be predicted with appropriate scaling factors. It should be stressed that further work is needed if that scaling is to be extended much beyond the relatively small size used here.

Another important observation concerns the effect of tough resin matrices. The instrumented falling weight impact test used in earlier work did not discriminate between materials during impact on the basis of strength or energy absorbed. It could have been argued at this stage that the properties during impact are seldom of the same importance as the properties after impact and that, as tough matrix composites suffer a reduced extent of impact damage compared to the isophthalic systems, then the tough systems should perform better under comparable post impact testing. It is true that tough systems such as those based on urethane-acrylates resins (GRP8) suffer less cracking for a given blow than those based on say an isophthalic (GRP7) but the inherent strengths of these materials are lower, figure 6. Figure 6 is significant because it calls into question the value of using tough matrices where other mechanical properties are sacrificed. Whereas the absolute reduction in strength for a given amount of damage is less for the ductile system than the brittle system, the percentage strength reduction is almost identical. Given that the tough system begins with an inferior strength this does not necessarily represent any advantage. GRP8 will exhibit a smaller area of damage than GRP7 for an equivalent impact and on the basis of absolute residual strengths after equivalent impacts there is little to choose between the two.

There can be serious detrimental effects of damage particularly an accentuation of environmental attack. Also this work has not been addressed the effects of scale in general and the effects of long term or intermittent loading. The long term durability of a composite is likely to depend on the growth rate of cracks. This in turn is likely to depend on the nature of cracks rather than merely their gross area. It could be confidently stated from this work that for small GRP structures that are likely to suffer impact or other forms of general abuse, the toughness of the matrix is not an important parameter in the short term. In the case of larger specimens and for long term durability, it is not sensible to make any comment at present.

Conclusions

A series of conclusions may be drawn from the results of this work. At this stage they must be considered as specific to small specimens tested in flexure.

The matrix has little influence on the properties of small GRP plates during impact and on residual strengths of such plates after impact.

Damage generally in GRP may be equated to a single drilled hole or a series of drilled holes where the cumulative width of the damage areas is similar in each case. No stress raising effect occurs due to holes or other forms of damage.

The results obtained from testing small specimens may be normalised to allow for geometric variations.

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References

1. Babic, Dunn and Hogg, *Plastics and Rubber Processing and Applications*, 1989 in press.

FIG 1 IMPACT NORMALISATION

18 COMBINATIONS OF MATRIX AND FIBRE CONFIGURATION
 ISO STANDARD CONDITIONS

FIG. 2 PLATE FLEXURE

SCHEMATIC EXPERIMENTAL CURVES

RADIOGRAPH

SCHEMATIC

FIG 3 BOX WITH CRACKS FROM IMPACT

FIG. 4 STRENGTH REDUCTION BY DAMAGE
SLOW LOADING III GRP7 18% V/V GLASS

FIG. 5: EFFECT OF HOLES ON REMAINING STRENGTH
SLOW LOADING III GRP7 18% V/V GLASS ONE SPECIMEN PER POINT

FIG. 6: EFFECT OF MATRIX DUCTILITY ON REMAINING STRENGTH

SLOW III 18% V/V GLASS ONE SPECIMEN PER POINT

FIG 7 GEOMETRIC NORMALISATION

SLOW LOADING III GRP7 18% V/V GLASS ONE SPECIMEN PER POINT